

NEON -Next Generation Integrated Energy Services for Citizen Energy Communities

WP 1- Integrated energy service co-creation and cross-sectoral arrangements

D1.4 End-user requirements matching services

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Executive summary

Currently, in the processes of implementation and deployment of Citizen Energy Communities, there is no systematic methodology for analysing the needs and requirements of energy end-users. There are attempts to take these user dimensions into account, but they remain fragmented and unstructured. As a result, there are hardly any basic principles for engaging efficiently with people in Citizen Energy Communities.

To propose a common strategy, this report first analyses the requirements and needs of existing or potential end-users of NEON's Citizen Energy Communities' case studies, considering the following aspects:

- **User types:**
 - Users are analysed from aspects such as gender, age or the type of legal or fiscal entity they conform such as residential or industrial.
- **Energy-related behaviour:**
 - Aspects related to the buildings themselves are analysed (insulation, whether there are attachments, electrical equipment installed in the systems, etc.).
- **Energy practices:**
 - Existing knowledge of the electricity tariff, the use of intelligent systems such as smart metres, etc.
- **Improvement fields:**
 - The possible energy improvement frameworks have been analysed as they are one of the most relevant aspects in the subsequent definition of the social and technological innovation.
- **Interest in energy:**
 - Analysis of the interest that energy arouses in the members of the communities such as environmental elements or renewable energies.
 - Once the sociological aspects related to energy use and its perception have been gathered and analysed, a guiding and systematised strategy for the engagement of the participants has been defined and established. To this end, an implementation guide structured in six fundamental phases has been designed.

The first phase is to identify the channels and tools to raise awareness and attract participants. The second phase is the analysis of the energy community itself, which in the case of the NEON project is made up of the pilots themselves. Thus, some of the cross-cutting methodologies have already been partially worked in WP1, such as individual interviews, so in this aspect the energy, economic, social, and environmental factors of each of the potential energy communities will be characterised. In the third phase, a promotion of the Citizen Energy Community will be carried out including the legal, organisational and inclusion mechanisms within the Energy Community. These mechanisms will include governance, business model and funding possibilities for the citizen energy community. The next phase will exploit participatory workshops as a tool for co-designing the Energy Community to promote learnings and bring the group together. For this purpose, a system of participatory sessions has been designed, ranging from the presentation of the project to the final presentation of the project's conclusions. Finally, phases five and six will define the constitution and implementation of the Citizen Energy Community.

D1.4 Leveraging the power of CECs and consumer perspective

This methodology will be implemented systematically in all the pilots during the project, so that as the last element of the document, the individual strategy adapted to each pilot has been defined, as well as the progress made to date in each of them.

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Introduction

Within the framework of action of Citizen Energy Communities (CECs), the technical and financial aspects usually dominate the destination and use of project resources, starting with a feasibility project and going through different phases such as the detailed design, installation and deployment of a virtual contracting and billing system that may have different innovative features depending on the needs of the participants that make up the community in question.

However, there is a fundamental aspect that is barely considered in most Energy Community deployment projects, and it is quite relevant in the definition of the community itself: social engagement. In fact, it is the very essence of the *raison d'être* of CECs. Energy Communities have as their principle the open and voluntary participation of the citizenry. This implies that the consideration of a sociological study that reveals the energy habits and needs, the technological deployments and the economic perception of the members of the community is a vital aspect to obtain long-term success in the service design, end-users' appropriation of the services and scalability of projects in which the community is the essential axis.

The first fundamental step for such a sociocultural understanding of engagement within the CECs is the identification of day-to-day practices and approaches to energy use, value and perception of this type of grouping of people and interests. The study of these factors confers to the project's approach a myriad (of elements, information, characteristics) beyond the merely technical aspects and allows to analyse in a more exhaustive and adapted way the need for integration of services and to structure an action plan for the implementation of these variables in the Energy Community.

Within the action space of the sociocultural understanding described above, this document analyses the most relevant aspects that shape end-users' behaviour(s) and perception(s) as well as their understanding(s) of the local and/or domestic (potentially) complex energy system(s). These aspects lead intrinsically to the corresponding analysis that defines, on the one hand, the needs of the participants of the CECs and, on the other hand, the characteristics of the existing services in the current technological state of the art. Therefore, the basic scheme that relates the needs and requirements of the Energy Communities with the services that are intended or can be implemented in that community is defined. Therefore, once this relationship has been established, it is possible to structure engagement strategies based on the actual and concrete needs of the citizens that make up the Energy Community.

This document will analyse in depth and detail the whole process described above starting from the understanding of potential and existing end-users' behaviour towards energy, mainly through the use of surveys, to the definition of the engagement strategy that is unequivocally based on the data of the previous studies.

1. Structure and implementation

To address the objectives and scope of the task, a methodology has been proposed, based on the social and human sciences (SSH), as well as human-centric and engagement tools. The structure of the work carried out followed a combination of participatory sessions among different partners to co-ideate concrete steps, as well as individual work of partners to implement or develop different sub-tasks. The steps followed are illustrated above.

STEPS	TIMELINE	PARTNERS INVOLVED
CEC characterization	February 2022	TRA, ENGIE, ALB, GRA, GFM
Design of field work to reveal end-user requirements	March 2022	TRA, FOSS
Dissemination of questionnaire to end-users of each CEC	March-April 2022	ENGIE, ALB, GRA, GFM
Questionnaire responses analyses	April 2022	TRA, FOSS
Engagement strategy approach	April 2022	TRA
Roadmap engagement strategies for each CEC	May-June 2022	TRA, ENGIE, ALB, GRA, GFM

Table 1 Engagement strategies development main steps

To kick off the task, the CEC characterisation allowed to map the existing technical and social ideas already developed and implemented. More importantly, it allowed the identification of existing and potential end-user types, as well as their level of commitment or understanding of the Neon project and Energy Community. After this diagnosis of each CEC, the field work was designed (Annex 01) with the objective of further revealing the end-user needs, energy behaviours, motivations, and interests to engage in the Energy Community. This not only included the creation of a questionnaire, but also designing the strategy to disseminate the survey, to reach end-users of different genders, age groups, and typologies (residents and non-residents; experts and non-experts). Once the questionnaires had been disseminated to each CEE and the responses collected, analysis took place and engagement strategies were designed to address the needs and requirements revealed. Finally, a specific engagement strategy was designed for each CEC to approach the idiosyncrasy of its end-users.

The alignment with other tasks was also achieved; the field work fed into the interviews and co-creation process that took place in task 1.4; and the end-user requirements will feed into the design of services along with task 1.5 (that yields more technical requirements).

2. End-User requirements

To match the services of CECs with the end-user requirements, the latter were revealed through questionnaires (Annex 01). Each CEC counts with a set of end-users; in the municipality of Berchidda (Italy), citizens, cork and wine enterprises, and public bodies will conform the community; in Villacañas (Spain), enterprises of the industrial park Polígono las Cabezas and residents of the neighbourhood; the residential resort Domaine de la Source (France) will count with residents; and the real estate complex for offices, Stains City (France) will be used by workers. Therefore, the questionnaire was designed for existing or potential residents, workers, public authorities, and enterprises as end-users of the CECs. Some questions did not apply to non-residents, and therefore were not answered by any end-users of Stains City (as it is a business park), and enterprises or public authorities of the other CECs.

This questionnaire has the aim of approaching the profile of household or building offices' that will participate in the community, energy-related behaviours, practices, and awareness of potential end-users. Therefore, this questionnaire is directed to citizens, public authorities or enterprises that will potentially participate in the Energy Communities of the Neon project.

The participation from each of the CEC in the questionnaire is shown in Figure 1, as it can be observed, 3 of the 4 CECs were able to get at least 19 participants, however the participation from Domaine de la Source was way below the other CECs. To be able to make comparisons between the CECs the results were analysed and presented in percentages.

Figure 1 Citizen Energy Communities

2.1 Types of end-users

The first block of questions was designed to determine where end-users stand in relation to their type of participation in the CEC, their gender, age and level of education. This information will be crucial to analyse the social demographics of each group of end-users, as well as integrate it to engagement strategies.

Figure 2 Relationship with the citizen energy communities

As it can be observed in Figure 2 the majority of the questionnaire’s respondents from all four CECs are residents of the CECs. Specifically, 100% of the respondents from Domaine de la Source and Berchidda are residents of the communities, given that these will only have this type of end-user. In addition, a large percentage of the respondents from Polígono las Cabezas (42%) are residents, but also 47% of the respondents are local workers, and a small percentage (11%) are electric car users. As expected, participants from Stains City are all workers. There is a significant representation of the diverse type of end-users of the CECs.

Figure 3 CECs participants age group

Regarding the age group to which end-users belong, the distribution among CECs is shown in Figure 3. Polígono las Cabezas and Stains City have similar percentages in age groups 18-34 with 42% and 48% respectively and for the age group 35-64 with 47% and 52% respectively. In addition, the age group 35-64

got the majority of the answers for Berchidda with 80%, with the rest of the respondents belonging to the age group of 18-34. Moreover, Domaine de la source has 75% of respondents that are 65 and up and 25% that belong to the age group 18-34. Therefore, Domaine de la Source has mostly an elderly population, different from the other CECs.

Figure 4 Gender of the CECs participants

The results for the gender of the participants are illustrated in Figure 4. Domaine de la Source respondents are all males, Polígono las Cabezas and Stains City have more males than females answering the questionnaires and Berchidda has more female respondents than males. Overall, the results show a slide edge towards male participants, which is especially notable in the Domaine de la Source CEC.

Figure 5 CECs participants Education Level

Figure 5 summarises the results for the level of education among the participants. The majority of the respondents in all four CECs have Tertiary education, equivalent or higher. Berchidda (26%), Polígono las

Cabezas (16%) and Stains City (10%) also have a small percentage of respondents with secondary education or equivalent. Finally, Polígono las Cabezas (21%) has a significant percentage of respondents with early childhood and primary education or equivalent. This data points at the potential technological or energy literacy of end-users, being in general quite high.

2.2 Energy-related behaviours

This set of questions are intended to reveal the energy behaviour of the end-users. This will help identify the most energy heavy activities in their everyday life and what is the current status of their buildings. Relevant information about the energy literacy that end-users have was also identified.

Figure 6 CECs Buildings Type

The types of building were only analysed for those CECs that have residents, so the business park Stains City does not count with any answers. According to the collected data and as shown in Figure 6, all the respondents from Domaine de la Source live in an apartment building. Moreover, 53% of the respondents for Polígono las Cabezas live in a detached building, 16% live in a semi-detached house and 11% in a central building. In addition, in Berchidda most of the respondents (58%) live in a detached building and the rest in a semi-detached building. The results show that many responders except from Domaine de la Source live in houses. This creates more opportunities regarding the activities the responders can participate in.

Figure 7 CECs building insulation level

As part of the questionnaire, participants were asked whether the building for which they are responding to the questionnaire as part of their CEC is well insulated. Domaine de la Source participants responded that their building is well insulated. Stains city respondents answered yes (62%) and a noticeable percentage answered that they are not aware (38%). Similarly, Poligono las Cabezas results showed that the majority of participants did not know if their building is well insulated (47%) and a significant percentage responded no (42%); 11% of the participants did not respond to the question. Finally, most of the participants from Berchidda (53%) answered no, 26% answered yes and 21% were not aware if their building was well insulated. The significant proportion of people that did not know how to answer the question shows a lack of knowledge about the energy dimensions of the building. This lack of data does not provide to what extent energy quality can be improved. It would be necessary to carry out a study of the insulation of the houses, and classify them with an Ecolabel, first to make the current state visible, and second to see the degree of improvement by becoming part of a CEC.

Figure 8 CECs Buildings refurbish aspects

To get an indication of what refurbish activities were performed in the past, participants were asked if their building was refurbished on three specific aspects: the envelope, equipment (HVAC, DHW) or with renewable energy systems. The results are illustrated in Figure 8. Poligono las Cabezas and Berchidda results show that refurbish activities were performed in all three aspects. Specifically, for Polígono las Cabezas, 26% answered that envelope refurbish was performed, 53% equipment refurbish and 11% added renewable energy sources systems. Moreover, 16% answered that the building was never refurbished and 21% did not know. Stains City participants responded that 14% refurbish their equipment, however, 43% answered that the building was never refurbished and 43% did not know. Finally, the data for Berchidda show that 16% refurbished the envelope, 26% the building’s equipment, and 26% added renewable energy sources systems. Also 32% answered that their building was never refurbished.

The results of the first three questions in this section can be used to pinpoint which refurbish activities can be performed and should be promoted to the CECs. However, since the answers of the participants are also based on how aware they are about these activities any conclusions need to be further validated. To analyse this further it was assumed that a safe category of refurbish activities, in terms of how easy it is to be identified by the participants, are the RES systems. Firstly, as shown by the responses presented in Figure 6, 100% of Poligono las Cabezas buildings are houses and according to the results illustrated in Figure 8 only 11% of the participants have RES systems installed. This highlights the untouched potential of installing RES systems in Poligono las Cabezas, something that would be easier since most buildings are houses. Similarly, the answers from Berchidda show the potential of RES systems in houses. By observing Figure 6 we can see that all responders from Berchidda live in a house and according to Figure 8 only 26% have a RES system installed. The data for Stains City as presented in Figure 8 cannot be used to extract any safe conclusions since 43% of the participants were not aware about any refurbish activities. Also, the low participation from Domaine de la Source does not provide certainty on any conclusions.

Figure 9 CEC buildings appliance usage

The participants were asked which appliances they use regularly. The results are shown in Figure 9. As it can be observed the responses from all the remaining CECs show that all the appliances' options are regularly used except the water dispenser. The study shows that several of the appliances related to the

thermal conditions of the home are used very frequently: air conditioning and hot water, therefore related to the use of energy. It has potential to improve, for example with the installation of DHW if they do not have it. The study shows that several of the appliances related to the thermal conditions of the home are used very frequently (air conditioning and hot water). The energy use has the potential to improve, for example with the installation of DHW, for those end-users that do not have it already.

2.3 Energy practices

This section of the questionnaire was formed with the aim to identify the energy practices in each CEC. This will help identify how aware the participants are regarding their energy practices and also which of the energy practices can be improved.

Figure 10 Energy bill impact on the CECs participants budget

To understand the impact of the energy bill of a household or an enterprise’s budget, the respondents were asked to rate this effect. A summary of the responses is given in Figure 10. Participants from Poligono las Cabezas answered that the energy bill has a very high impact (47%) or high impact (53%) on their budget. In addition, the majority of Stains City respondents (67%) didn’t know the impact of the energy bill for the enterprise that they are working for, which points at the lack of energy literacy that workers have regarding consumption of their workplace. Moreover, 14% responded with high impact, 10% with medium impact and 10% with low impact. In addition, the majority of participants from Domaine de la Source responded that they are not aware about the impact of the energy bill (50%), 25% mentioned that it has a high impact and the other 25% that it does not have any impact on their budget. Berchidda results show the most variety in answers. The majority of the respondents answered that the energy bill has medium impact on their budget (37%), the options of very high impact and high impact had the same results with 26% each and finally low impact and no impact had 5% of the responses each. Overall, the results showed that a large percentage of the responders (25.4%) is not aware of how impactful the energy

bill is on their household or an enterprise’s budget. This lack of information shows a deficiency, which could be approached with training sessions on electricity bills and the electricity market. A greater awareness of consumption, and of the options they have, for example according to the type of installed power, could lead to improvements, not only in the electricity bill, but also in the efficiency of use.

Figure 11 Electricity tariff used for the energy billing

The participants were asked what kind of electricity tariff they have in order to get an indication if they are aware of what electricity tariffs are used for their billing. The data collected is illustrated in Figure 11. As expected, most workers in Stains City did not know what kind of electricity tariff is used (81%), 5% selected the fixed price tariff, 10% the dynamic tariff and 5% selected the two-block period tariff. Many respondents from Poligono las Cabezas selected the two-block tariff as their electricity tariff (42%), 16% selected the fixed price tariff, 5% the dynamic tariff and 26% did not know what kind of electricity tariff they are using. From Domaine de la Source, 75% selected the fixed price tariff and 25% did not know. Finally, the majority of Berchidda participants did not know what electricity tariff is used in their building (58%), 26% selected fixed price tariff, 11% choose the more than two-block period hourly tariff and 5% selected others. Overall, the data indicate that most of the participants (54%) are not aware of what electricity supply tariffs are used for their energy bill. As previously mentioned, the lack of knowledge could be satisfied with training workshops about the regulation of tariffs.

Figure 12 Energy produced by the CECs

Figure 12 shows the results for the question, “Is energy produced in your dwelling or office building?”. Most respondents for Poligono las Cabezas (74%) responded no and the rest answered yes. Similarly, 68% of Berchidda respondents answered no with the rest 32% answering yes. In addition, 67% of participants from Stains City did not know if there is energy production in their building, 24% answered no and 5% responded yes. Similar results can be observed for Domaine de la Source, 50% did not know if their energy production in their building. Also 25% answered yes and 25% answered no. From the results obtained to this question, it seems that they do not have much local energy production, which opens a new opportunity, since being able to produce local energy would entail a series of advantages for the beneficiaries and could be an impetus to establish a CEC.

Figure 13 Smart Appliances at Home

To get an idea of how many and what smart appliances are used in the CECs the participants were asked to report if they have any smart appliances at home. The results are illustrated in Figure 13. Stains City had the most variety in responses with 38% answering that they have a smart air condition, 29% smart lighting controllers, 14% smart television, 10% Wi-Fi lamps and finally 5% selected a smart water boiler. In addition, as it can be observed Berchidda had variety in the responses as well, 42% selected the smart television, 11% a washing machine, 5% selected smart sockets and 5% air condition. Moreover, Poligono las Cabezas only responses were for smart sockets and lighting controllers with 5% each. Finally, only 25% of respondents from Poligono las Cabezas reported that they own a smart washing machine. The number of smart devices is low and insignificant in almost all cases. Also, smart TVs are not necessarily a much more efficient appliance than a non-smart TV. Based on the results obtained, except in Stains City, there is hardly any efficient use of energy through smart devices.

Figure 14 Electricity Smart Meter

To get an indication of how many buildings have an electricity smart metre the participants were asked to respond on if their house or building has a smart metre installed. The results are shown in Figure 14. The most popular answer from Poligono las Cabezas was No with 58%, yes was second with 26% and 16% was not aware if they have a smart metre. Most participants from Stains City (52%) answered yes however the remaining 48% were not aware of if they have an electricity smart metre. All the participants from Domaine de la Source confirm that they have a smart metre installed in their home. Finally, 32% of the respondents from Berchidda answered yes, 42% answered no and 26% were not aware. The results show very low data regarding the intelligent control, therefore efficient, of the use of electricity. This mainly affects the recording of consumption, since if it is not done with a smart metre, it is subject to other forms of measurement that can lead to errors, and to an abuse of the "estimated value" concept, which can have a negative impact on the cost of electricity to be paid by users.

Figure 15 Means of transport used by the CECs participants

A goal of the questionnaire was to understand what means of transport people use in the CECs, which could point at the potential of raising awareness about energy saving or sustainability. The results are given in Figure 17. All the participants from Poligono las Cabezas use a car or a motorbike and 5% of them also walk. A large percentage from Stains City (57%) uses public transport but participants also use a bike/scooter/skateboard (19%), a car or motorbike (19%) and a small percentage of people are used to walk (5%). All the respondents from Domaine de la Source use walking as a means of transport, 75% also use a car or motorbike and 25% also use public transport. Finally, all participants from Berchidda only use cars or motorbikes for transport. Overall, the results across the CECs show that the use of public transport is not a popular way of transport. Most end-users use the car or motor vehicle, there is a low use of public transport and, except in Domaine de la Source, there is hardly any walking. This shows a potential within the Energy Community, to stimulate a cultural shift to promote mobility by walking, biking, or using public transport.

Cross cutting an ecological transition perspective to the design of services of the Energy Communities, it is worth highlighting that electric car ownership raises equity issues such as the access to clean technology, urban design, health and wellbeing due to immobility, among others. Promoting sustainable and healthy cities and rural areas implies limiting the use of cars to those that are necessary, thus, considering the electrification of the fleet (charging points, etc.) should be linked to sustainable transport plans to work with a broader vision that prioritises other modes (e.g public transport, biking or walking). The use of one mode or another will be related to other factors, probably infrastructural and urban (proximity, density) and partly also socio-cultural. But as a general conclusion, greater car use does not necessarily indicate a potential for electrification (which could freeze the modal split), but for shifting car trips to other modes, following the inverted mobility pyramid. The same occurs with buses and bicycles, which should not all be electrified, but priority should be given to walking, conventional bicycles, and then introducing electric motorization when necessary. Therefore, the services of the CECs must consider holistic sustainable mobility modes, beyond electrification and car use.

Figure 16 Electric Vehicle usage

To get an indication of the presence of electric vehicles in the CECs the participants were asked if they owned an EV vehicle. The results are given in Figure 18. As it can be observed the large majority of participants in all four CECs do not have an EV. More specifically, all the respondents of Domaine de la Source confirm that they don't have an EV. Similarly, most participants from Berchidda (95%) do not have an EV and a small percentage of 5% responded that they own a pure EV vehicle. In addition, responses from Polígono las Cabezas have similar results with 79% responding that they don't own an EV and 21% reporting that they have a pure EV. Finally, the same pattern was observed from Stains City, 81% responded that they don't own an EV, however the results from Stains City had also the most variety, 10% own a pure EV, 5% have a non-plug-in hybrid EV and lastly 5% have a plug-in hybrid EV. Overall, the large majority (86%) of participants do not have an EV.

2.4 Interest in energy

To identify the interest that end-users have in engaging in energy related projects such as Energy Communities, a series of questions were asked about their motivations, wants and needs related to energy.

Figure 17 CECs participants motivations

The participants were asked about their motivations for joining their local CEC. The results are illustrated in Figure 19. The most popular answer among the participants from all 4 CECs was the economic savings on energy expenses from electricity bills with 96.8%. The next two most popular responses were to gain energy self-sufficient and to replace fossil fuels with renewable energy sources, with 74.6% and 73% respectively. The percentages for the other community, environmental and social motivations were relatively balanced between 66.7% and 58.73%. Therefore, there seems to be a predominantly economic incentive, but environmental and social drives also play an important role in engaging end-users.

Figure 18 Relationship between energy consumption and environmental protection

The participants were asked if they think there is a relationship between energy consumption and environmental protection. Figure 20 shows that none of the participants from all four CECs stated that there is almost no relation. In addition, Poligono las Cabezas and Stains City had similar responses with the option ‘there is a certain relationship’ getting 42% and 43% respectively and the option ‘there is a tight relationship’ getting 58% and 57% respectively. All responses from Berchidda were the same with ‘there is a certain relationship’. This shows how end-users are aware about the environmental impact that energy behaviours have, which aligns with their interest to decrease environmental damage through more renewable sources and more informed decision making.

Figure 19 Knowledge of real-time energy consumption

The respondents were asked if they think it would be helpful to know their real-time energy consumption and how they want to access it. The results in Figure 21 show that participants from Berchidda answered positively with the option to access it through a mobile app. Most of Stains city’s respondents answered yes with a 57% difference in the option of accessing the information, 38% selected a mobile app and 29% a web browser. Also 33% stated that they don’t need this information. In comparison, the majority of Domaine de la Source (75%) responses do not think it is helpful to know this information and 25% state that it would be helpful and want to access it through a mobile app. This yields important information about how to design an app for end-users to follow their daily energy consumption. For instance, in Domaine de la Source it might be needed to inform about the benefits of tracking energy consumption to promote beneficial changes in their behaviours.

Figure 20 Familiarity with self-consumption

The participants were asked how familiar they are with self-consumption. The results are illustrated in Figure 22 and illustrate that all respondents from Domaine de la Source stated that they fully understand the concept of self-consumption. In addition, most responses from Stains City also responded that they fully understand self-consumption, 24% stated that they understand it except for some concepts, 10% responded that they don’t fully understand it and finally 14% said that they don’t understand it at all. Similarly, the results from Poligono las Cabezas showed 47% answering that they fully understand the concept, 42% stating that they understand it except for some concepts and finally 11% stating that they only understand it partially. The same trend was followed with the results of Berchidda, the answers that ‘they fully understand the concept’ and that ‘they understand with some exception’ received 32% each, also 21% responded that they only understand it partially and 16% that only understand it at all. All in all, the level of energy literacy seems to be relatively low in all CECs, signalling that there will be challenges to be tackled through training sessions or other methods of learning.

Figure 21 Willingness to participate in NEON activities

Part of the questionnaire’s goals was to get an idea of the willingness of end-users to participate and benefit from the possibilities that are presented in the NEON project. The results are shown in Figure 23. Most participants from Polígono las Cabezas were positive in joining NEON project’s activities with 42% answering that they are willing to join if there is sufficient retribution, and 47% responding that they are willing to join if it’s not affecting their comfort levels. Moreover, 16% are not willing to join since they don’t want to change their consumption patterns at any time, 5% mentioned that they don’t trust external companies to have control over their devices and access to their consumption data and finally 5% answered that they don’t know and therefore they don’t have an opinion. In addition, all the participants from Domaine de la Source are willing to partake in the activities of NEON but 75% want a sufficient retribution and 5% want to ensure that it will not affect their comfort levels. Most of the participants from Berchidda (63%) are willing to join the activities if there is sufficient retribution and others (16%) are positive but want assurances that it will not affect their comfort levels. There seems to be a high willingness of end-users to participate in activities of the Neon project, with a special interest in knowing the benefits of these.

2.5 Domains for potential energy savings

Figure 22 Energy consumption reduction

The respondents were asked if they think it is possible to reduce their monthly energy consumption. The results are shown in Figure 25. Polígono las Cabezas results are as follows: 42% answered that it is almost impossible to reduce their monthly energy consumption, 37% believe that a small reduction can be achieved and 21% state that they anticipate a significant reduction. Many participants from Stains City (71%) believe that it is possible to have a small reduction of their energy consumption and 29% believe that it is almost impossible to reduce their consumption. As it can be observed the results for Domaine de la Source are balanced between a small reduction and significant reduction. Finally, responses from Berchidda show that 47% answered that a small reduction is possible, 47% responded that a significant reduction can be achieved and 5% answered that it is almost impossible to achieve an energy reduction. Overall, most end-users seem to perceive there is room to reduce their energy consumption, although in Polígono las Cabezas there is quite a high percentage of respondents that find it difficult to see how this could be done. Again, this points at the current sociocultural behaviours and knowledge about energy and a need of gaining knowledge about how demand flexibility could reduce their energy consumptions.

Figure 23 Automatic control and monitoring agreement

The participants were asked if they would agree that their retailer (or another company) could monitor and operate their electronic devices automatically, without affecting their comfort with the aim to provide service to the grid. The results are shown in Figure 26. Most of the participants from Polígono las Cabezas (63%) responded that it depends and 37% were negative. With 75% Domaine de la Source’s participants responding yes and 25% stating that they would do it under some circumstances. 71% of Stains City responses were positive and 29% were negative. Lastly, 74% of respondents from Berchidda answered yes, 21% it depends and 5% no. In general, end-users show a positive inclination towards having automatic control and monitoring, if this meets some requirements that would have to be revealed in future moments. In general, end users show a positive inclination to have automatic control and monitoring, if this meets some requirements that should be revealed at a later date. It is important to inform well about the advantages of monitoring to clear up doubts, especially in Polígono las Cabezas where it seems that they show more mistrust.

2.6 Set of end-user requirements

As a result of the questionnaire answers forwarded by existing and potential end-users of all CECs of the Neon project, a set of end-user requirements have been extracted. These requirements point at the key incentives that end-users must engage in their local CEC. As per the field work conducted, end-user requirements can be summed up in two: community dynamics, and technological tools.

<p>Learn about energy: understanding energy bills and energy behavioural changes</p> <p>Make decisions to be energy self-sufficiency</p> <p>Transparency of the contracts and data usage</p> <p>Promote the use of public transport where it is available.</p> <p>Educate people about the benefits of EV vehicles</p>	<p>Track economic and environmental savings</p> <p>Tips for demand-side flexibility and reduce energy consumption</p> <p>Easy to understand daily and hourly information about energy production and consumption</p>
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3. Engagement strategies

Engagement strategies are an important resource for CEC leaders to plan ways in which to involve end-users and promote the co-design of the community. For that, a general proposal of an engagement strategy was created as a guide. Instead of a solution that fits all, it was a compilation of ideas and pillars to be adapted to the specific case of the different CECs of Neon.

The general objective of Energy Communities' Engagement Plan is to involve stakeholders, providing them with the necessary information, spaces and tools. The democratisation of energy revolves around providing end-users of energy and other local actors what they need to make energy-related decisions along the value chain and lead the path towards a clean and just energy transition. This entails a cultural change that implies giving more importance to energy, and empowering women, people from lower classes, migrants, people living in poverty or with a disability, to get involved in renewable energy production and consumption. The consolidation of a community takes time, meetings between people, coordination of participants and the creation of links. A series of phases are proposed to tackle different aspects of engagement roadmaps, including communication and awareness-raising, analysis of the CEC pilots, ideation of legal, economic-financial, organisational, and social inclusion formulas.

Phase 1: Awareness raising and recruitment, suggests identifying the channels and tools to recruit and raise awareness among participants. The alliance with the communication team will be crucial for the implementation of graphic design methods in door-to-door visits, emails, flyers, posters, social media, or articles.

Phase 2: Analysis of the pilot, proposes to characterise the pilots in its energy, economic, social, and environmental aspects. Some methods already being conducted in the frame of Work Package 1 of Neon are interviews, stakeholder maps, a pilot characterization, and questionnaires. These research activities may yield critical information about the needs, wants, motivation and possibilities to codesign an enriching and well-functioning CEC.

Phase 3: Promotion of the energy community, is about planning the legal, organisational and inclusion mechanisms within the Energy Community. To devise the governance model, the business model and funding possibilities should be devised. It could also be of interest in many cases the alliance with public authorities with data and access to social services or gender inequalities.

Phase 4: Creation of the leading group and collective ideation process highlights the potential of participatory workshops to codesign with existing/potential participants of the Energy Community, promote learnings and unite the group. Creating an active group is crucial for the consolidation of CECs, and for that, periodic encounters, celebrations and moving towards a common vision made of agreements is crucial. Some ideas for possible sessions are:

- Session 1: Present project and participants. Important to introduce what is the project, and who are the people involved in it. Especially necessary if there are a lot of new end-users. It's an exercise of welcoming, introducing, and celebrating the kick off. There is a symbolic meaning to new beginnings and related to planting a seed in an energy transition that will enable the proactivity of end-users.

- Session 2: Identify needs, motivations, and expectations. Consists of a moment to share and empathise the needs and wants of different end-users in a dialogical way. Will allow further plan actions and an organisational model that suits these needs.
- Session 3: Envisioning future scenarios. The ideation of future possible scenarios of the Energy Community implies co-ideating proposals to how to build a community and respond to all needs. For example, how will people learn things they don't know and need to know to make informed decisions about energy (digital tool), how will the encounters be of the community (periodic or not, to make decisions, organise sensitive, community-based uses, share experiences and tracking energy consumption), how will the group communicate, etc.
- Session 4: Governance workshop. It is useful when there's not an entity created yet (association, cooperative) and to decide the organisational model and next steps.
- Session 5: Final presentation. Important to present to neighbours or significant people for the CEC participants. It can also be a moment to celebrate the process and creation of the leading group for it to be autonomous.

Phases 5 and 6 about constituting and implementing the CEC have to do with the formal or bureaucratic steps needed, and the official launch.

Figure 24 CECs engagement strategies

a. CEC 01: Berchidda (Italy)

- Pilot leader: Gridability/R2M Energy

Berchidda's CEC will be established on a totally voluntary basis by the part of the population interested in actively participating in the management of their electricity grid with the support of the Municipality, that is in this particular case the DSO of its own grid, and of the Energy manager experts involved in this project (Gridability, R2M Energy, Prosume, Energy4Com, AXPO). The key stakeholders are the inhabitants of the city of Berchidda, consumers, producers and prosumers that produce locally green energy from their private PV plants or that are interested in joining and participating actively in the energy transition of their town.

Phase 1: Awareness-raising and recruitment

For Berchidda, the main strategic channels to raise awareness and recruit end-users will be social media and local journals. These will have the goal of involving as many people as possible, including the elderly population and emigrants.

The institutional website of the Municipality of Berchidda and the official Facebook page (which has more than 2.000 followers) provide all news and workshops related to the Energy Community. These two channels are especially addressed to residential users. A Telegram channel of about 350 followers is also managed by the Municipality and is used to inform citizens of Berchidda about the CEC. Gridability will take advantage of this efficient communication tool to send periodic messages to the citizens on the Energy Community and project's activities with the support of the Municipality.

To further increase the involvement of the community, it is also planned to send customised "pills" on Energy Community themes specially prepared by experts in the Sardinian language. This will involve all the people who use Berchidda's typical dialect. This will target different age groups; thus, it is possible to leverage the deep sense of belonging to the community.

Traditional communication channels such as local journals will also be a great asset. Currently, the number of citizens that read newspapers in Berchidda (in paper or digital form) is still remarkable. For this reason, short articles and press releases in the most important regional newspapers (e.g., L'Unione Sarda, La Nuova Sardegna, etc.) will play a significant role and also enable reaching a big part of the population, elderly people, that do not use digital communication tools.

Phase 2: Analysis of the pilot

A thorough exploration of the pilot is being conducted through interviews and workshops with end-users of SMEs, citizens and the municipality of Berchidda, which helped analyse the needs, motivations and pain points of different stakeholders. Interviews were conducted in March and April, and in mid-April a public workshop was organised and opened to all residents. The results from the interviews were presented and discussed on that occasion with all the municipality assembly (as reported in D1.2).

Gridability, in alliance with the sister project HESTIA, conducted a "Gender and inclusiveness" workshop with the population of Berchidda and a women's focus group in mid-April. This session allowed collection of the viewpoint and experiences of women participating in the project. Activities targeting women are key to exploit the full potential of Demand Response (DR). This is because women in pilots with a traditional gender role, such as Berchidda, are the main responsible for DR actions within households: hence the success of any project depends on their understanding and active engagement in the process.

Phase 3: Promotion of the Energy Community

Gridability will assist the municipality in collecting expressions of interests from citizens, which will lay the ground for the constitution of a novel cooperative. The cooperative will be open to the participation of any citizens and company residents in the area covered by the municipality's grid, including users in the agricultural sector of the grid.

The Italian regulation sets the following two main conditions to formalise a Renewable Energy Community (REC): (1) Open door, that is, freedom of participants to enter and leave whenever you wish; and (2) Non-profit.

Following these conditions, the available legal forms to create a CEC are the association or cooperative. The association is a simpler and cheaper solution from the administrative point of view, but the Italian laws (Italian Civil Code) state that all members are jointly and severally liable for the activity of the Community. Whereas within the cooperative, an advantage is that the risk of insolvency is attributed to the cooperative as a legal entity and not to the members. However, it is more expensive and time-consuming from the administrative side. Thus, the associative form is more adapted when the sole purpose is the redistribution of the incentive, and there is nothing else to manage; no power plants or infrastructure that would need investments, and no services that are allowed by the CEC. While, in the case of Berchidda, it was decided that it is preferable to form a cooperative to encourage members to invest in private power plants and enhance investments in infrastructures. Additionally, with the Municipality as one of its members, larger public buildings and properties can be included, and public funds can be used. Moreover, as in this specific case the Municipality of Berchidda is also DSO of its own grid (AEC), by including them in the community, the CEC can take advantage of their expertise and their services on grid distribution and maintenance.

Gridability will work by interacting with the service providers involved, specifically AXPO and the Municipality for Berchidda. We will provide the PROSUME Platform for the Governance of the Community and the deployment of the Business Logics which will be implemented throughout the "Smart Contract" automation as implied within the PROSUME Platform technology.

Regarding the development of financing and innovative business schemes, the idea is to further successfully implement logics which can provide revenues within the Community and for the parties involved (to be conducted in Task 2.2).

Phase 4: Creation of the leading group and collective ideation process of the CEC

To approach the different needs, wants and motivations for end-users and stakeholders to engage in the CEC, key engagement activities will be used, such as interviews and workshops. Interviews with stakeholders (as reported in D1.2) serve for the identification of key pain points and opportunities, and help envision the pathway for participatory workshops. Interactive sessions with residents and key stakeholders:

- Session 1: Common vision interactive (September, 2022): inform about the potential of CECs, exchange ideas in order to build their own
- Session 2: Future scenario workshops (November, 2022): Devising future scenarios of the CEC, alongside residents, and the Municipality, to co-ideate how the CEC could operate and promote the active participation of different actors

Phase 5: Legal constitution of the community

The constitution of the community is expected for September 2022. According to Italian law, the minimum membership fee is 25€, then proceeds in multiples of 25 euros. The Berchidda CEC will adopt the following entry policy (depending on the type of member):

- Individuals and households: the minimum share;
- Non-profit associations: 50€;
- SMEs: 50€ for the less energy-intensive and 100 for the more energy-intensive.

Participants will also have to download the Prosume app, which will handle individual and collective Demand Response remuneration mechanisms based on Italian regulations and whatever rules are established by the community. The Prosume app will serve to redistribute the incentive to the members of the community. A first version of the app for Berchidda will be released in July, when a participatory workshop to co-design smart contracts with citizens will be planned. There will be expert and non-expert participants; for the latter, informational sessions will be organised to raise awareness, clear doubts and provide key information about energy. Following Italian regulation, people will be elected to be part of the cooperative's Board of Directors.

Phase 6: Official kick off (by the end of the Neon project)

b. CEC 02 : Domaine de la Source-Villard de Lans (France)

- Pilot leader: Albedo

Domaine de la Source is a set of 3 buildings and 25 dwellings located in a famous ski resort in the Alps mountains. The council is very motivated to push the development of an Energy Community.

Phase 1: Awareness-raising and recruitment

In Domaine de la Source (DDLs), the council is formed by 7 people representing all the occupants. This group shows great motivation to participate in an Energy Community, however, to further engage other residents' door-to-door visits or massive broadcasts will be the method used.

Within the Neon project, an exploratory video will be disseminated among end-users to explain the benefits of collective self-consumption, what are CECs and what are the gains for end-users, could be a strong tool to raise awareness.

Phase 2: Analysis of the pilot

In order to understand and better design engagement actions, efforts to characterise the energy, economic, social and environmental dimensions have been forwarded. Interviews, questionnaires and meetings were used to clarify the model of energy self-consumption suitable for the CEC. These interviews were made in the form of individual meetings with the members of the council, consisting of technical explanations of the self-consumption process and technical explanation of the DDLs installations.

Phase 3: Promotion of the Energy Community

As in all self-consumption in France, it is needed to create a legal entity called *Personne Morale Organisatrice* (PMO). A PMO can be a company or an association. The PMO administrator must be either a consumer or a producer of local energy, groups all the participants, energy producers and consumers, and is responsible for the exchanges with grid managers and energy producers for the additional energy supply.

The steps to follow, in order to create an Energy Community are:

1. Organise a group with the producer and consumers, that should be equipped with smart metres.
2. Create the *Personne Morale Organisatrice* (PMO); it could be a society, an association, or a social housing society. In the statutes of this organisation the rules to exchange electricity should be defined (specifically the sharing method which could be fixed or dynamic).
3. Declare the production in self consumption on the grid manager (in the [Enedis website](#))
4. Write/adapt the convention between PMO and Enedis and sign it with Enedis
5. Once Enedis has launched the community

Phase 4: Creation of the leading group and collective ideation process of the CEC

The design of the Energy Community is being done primarily through meetings with the DDLs committee which is shown to be important because we establish a link of trust between Albedo (CEC leader) and the DDLs.

DDLS' committee is composed of all the flat owners and is elected by the owner's assembly every 3 years. Regular meetings and phone calls with the DDLS committee have shown to be an effective method to ideate and push forward key steps.

In Domaine de la Source, the following sessions are planned to forward a collective ideation process:

- Session 1: Present project and participants at the General Assembly of owners (September 2022)
- Session 2: Technical workshop with DDLS committee (September 2022)
- Session 3: Letter of engagement that confirms the will of DDLS to work with Neon project through Albedo energie (October 2022)
- Session 4: Governance workshop (November 2022)

Phase 5: Legal constitution of the community

The general assembly will be held on Sept 22nd of 2022, and it will be decided to launch the legal community.

Phase 6: Official kick off by November/December 2022

c. CEC 03: Industrial Park Las Cabezas (Spain)

- Pilot leader: GFM

The Spanish CEC is located in an industrial park in Villacañas, Spain. Companies and factories from the industrial park, citizens from the city of Villacañas or owners of electrical cars are potential end-users. The CEC Las Cabezas already has a 300kWp PV installation and an EV charging station which involve important stakeholders. According to those installations, an energy storage system will be available for a better flexibility of the system, helping to bring energy storage from the PV modules during the non-solar hours.

Businesses of the industrial park are interesting because they can become an end-user in the first step and an energy producer after being part of the CEC. Those situations will help escalate the members to a higher level bringing more energy producers, energy consumers and more flexibility to the system. Promoting an Energy Community of mixed profiles, combining residential and productive social agents will be the best situation for the development of the community.

Phase 1: Analysis of the pilot

The exploration of needs, wants, motivations and expectations of end-users is proposed to identify how to design the CEC and propose awareness raising and recruitment activities. Three types of stakeholders have been interviewed (19 people respond to the questionnaire): end-users (residential, industries or service providers), energy providers (energy generators based on solar renewable energies) and service providers (EV chargers, storage managers based on LFP batteries) (results presented in D 1.2).

This research is leading to a proposal of a CEC based on a virtual money and energy saving balance. Such organisational form allows for end users' decentralised distribution, so they can take advantage of energy provided by the existing services, in spite of not being directly connected, and also allocated in different cities or villages.

The CEC will have a virtual money bag filled with all the revenues of stakeholders who have energy-based businesses (Such as PV generation or the EV charging point, for example). End-users will contribute to the money bag with payments of the energy consumed from the CEC, helping the service producers maintain their activities and enjoying a better price from their energy consumed. To make the economic distribution, a model will balance the consumption and generation of energy by every stakeholder.

Phase 2: Awareness-raising and recruitment

The CEC in Villacañas will rely on the closeness with the local people and the word of mouth, as it is a small town. A year ago, GFM started talking about the project with local people, with whom they have a relationship of trust. Given the rise in electricity prices, the idea of a CEC resonated; this is how recruitment began.

In order to raise awareness about energy, specific workshops and communication materials will be developed. Flyers and brochures will be provided to the stakeholders of the CEC. The documents and flyers will carry technical and economic information, explained in a simple way to be understood by most people (including non-experts of energy). The brochures will provide information on:

- Ideas for the operation of the Energy Community.

- The service offered by the CEC to enjoy the advantages of consuming energy during the no solar period, because of the energy storage system without making the initial investment of a PV installation.
- Prices of the service and the advantages for each stakeholder group.
- How their needs could be solved and also, some possible advantages they could not have taken in account.
- Success cases applied to the needs of end-users.

Social media is also a strong means for recruitment of the younger end-users. For these channels, a small video with information of the project would be helpful.

Phase 3: Promotion of the Energy Community

To consolidate the CEC, an association will be created to manage the savings achieved each month, the consumption of each member (and also if their consumptions have been modified by the community) and how the monetization of the energy savings generated by GFM will be distributed. A percentage of that amount will be reserved for management costs, which will be decided among the members of the Energy Community. The rest of the savings should be distributed between the members according to their agreements with the community.

Steps to create that association will be:

1. Define the main representatives of the community. The representatives will be elected by each group of stakeholders by voting.
2. Define the categories of the community members, as well as their rights and obligations.
3. Define the rules of the membership, including rights and obligations.
4. Establish minimum levels of production and consumption as well as incentives and penalties as appropriate. This will depend on each type of member, his value in the CEC and flexibility in consumption/service.
5. Draft contracts for each type of community member. The contracts will contain all the information including obligations, rights, penalties and rewards.

Regarding more technical aspects of the Energy Community promotion, the engagement process will feed into the app development. Some initial ideas to be tested with stakeholders is to have a platform that shows the economic and energy savings, energy consumed from the community and environmental impact.

For the promotion of the Energy Community, working groups will be created to focus on statutes, economics, training, communication, etc. Trying to ensure that everyone had representation of different profiles. For it to be a participatory community, support will be provided in the form of facilitation of workshops and training, and places where groups can work freely. The work carried out in the groups will intend to cater to the different needs of different users, who have different interests.

The public authorities could help for example, creating an entity of energy provider for example, and taking part of the CEC, or they could become an end-user. Also, those CEC can help on how the neighbours see their representatives, promoting the CEC and its advantages. However, now, the municipality has shown to be uninterested, so this will have to be something to explore once the community is more developed.

Phase 4: Creation of the leading group and collective ideation process of the CEC

The main objective of the Energy Community in Villacañas is to enable everyone to participate in the energy transition. The proposal of GFM is that they will be the provider of photovoltaic self-consumption with storage, and the leader of the CEC. The individual self-consumption and energy surplus could be potentially used to compensate the economic savings generated by self-consumption to the project's Energy Community members. The monetization of the energy saved will be distributed among all the members of the Energy Community according to the consumption of each home/vehicle. Apart from economic savings, it is intended to incentivize energy savings, empowering people with tools and information to be able to change their behaviour and consume less.

This is an initial proposal for the Energy Community, that will be contrasted and further developed with the participants. For that, the following workshops will be planned:

- Session 1: Workshop to identify needs, pain points etc. with stakeholders (September 2022)
- Session 2: Future scenario workshop to envision possibilities (September 2022)
- Session 3: Governance workshop to co-ideate the way the association will operate and agree on the statutes of the association (October 2022)

The most critical sessions will be those regarding the envisioning of future scenarios, to collectively establish the technical framework and the financial framework to develop a favourable CEC. For such, it is necessary to clearly establish which are the variables within the community and establish the technical relationships between each one of them to define the model that adjusts the functioning of each member within the community.

Some difficulties that can be foreseen have to do with the recruitment of interested and potential end-users, given the complexity of the project.

Phase 5: Legal constitution of the community

The installation from the technical point of view should be developed after the legal constitution of the community. For that, it will be necessary to establish what each member of the community can contribute and how it could be integrated or related to the rest of the members.

It will be necessary to establish a model that correlates the set of variables where the value of the system to be optimised is the total savings of each of the members of the community based on their contributions. For this, it will be sought that the savings of the members be the maximum.

Once the technical aspects have been fixed, the technical equipment would be installed by the members to control such variables and be able to have the value of these data in a system.

For this reason, although the constitution of the community can probably take place in a period of 4 to 6 months, the development from the technical point of view could take a long time and could reach 9 or 10 months.

Phase 6: Official kick off (by the end of the Neon project)

d. CEC 04: Stains City business park (France)

- Pilot leader: ENGIE

Stains City's CEC currently consists of 2 office sites, within an area of approximately 34,500m²:

- Industreet: An innovative training campus for energy professions and trades. It owns 186 KWC PV production installed on the roof. Regarding production and storage of hydrogen, Industreet is interested in its development for mobility and infrastructure.
- ENGIE Crigen: ENGIE Corp. Research Centre, working on innovation in the different vectors of energy and developing hydrogen technologies.

The community has been co-created by ENGIE and Industreet, which are the core stakeholders of this community. However, other stakeholders could impact the community in a direct manner and will be interacting with the service users as ENOGRID (a service provider), the facility manager, the energy provider and Hydrogen Lab-ENGIE CRIGEN, and indirect stakeholders that will not have interacted with the CEC services such as the DSO, assets and properties managers, equipment's manufacturer, and technical experts.

Phase 1: Awareness-raising and recruitment

The recruitment was done through door-to-door visits, to meet the training centre responsible (Director Site manager). E-mails and physical meetings are being used for communication and consolidation of the Energy Community.

Phase 2: Analysis of the pilot

The co-creation process has been conducted, with the inputs of Industreet's director, the IT manager, the maintenance manager, and the site manager. In such a process, four services have been identified and two of them could be immediately implemented: collective self-consumption and Hydrogen production from renewable energy.

Phase 3: Promotion of the Energy Community

The legal and organisational mechanisms that the Energy Community will have, entail the following steps:

- Creation of an association to act as a corporate body, assigning a PMO (Organising Moral Person) for the collective self-consumption operation of the members (ENGIE and IDUSTREET for now). In the status of this organisation, the rules will define how the self-consumption is done and the method to be used (fixed or dynamic)
- Manage the community with DSO: signature of the agreement, addition/removal of participants, management of distribution keys
- ENOGRID will support ENGIE and INDUSTREET for the technical and administrative set-up of projects and for the collective self-consumption operation and management of interactions with ENEDIS
- Define decision-making processes for community management (including an annual GA)

- Define the statutes based on the prerequisites of the PMO
- Design contracts between producers (Industreet) and consumers (ENGIE) directly (to be conducted in task 2.2). The PMO can follow up on any invoicing between members
- Evaluate how the H2 production could be shared at the community level

A collaboration with the DSO which is the public power provider, is crucial to agree on the power to be injected to their grid from the PV that Industreet owns.

The techno-economic study has been done, the PV installation and the hydrogen production are already existing, as well as the connection to the main grid. The support needed for the set-up is financed by both ENGIE and Industreet

Phase 4: Creation of the leading group and collective ideation process of the CEC

The sessions or actions that have already been carried out in the CEC are bi-weekly meetings with the IT manager, the maintenance manager, the site manager, and the lab FTB, to follow-up the set-up of the community. Further technical meetings to determine the technical specifications of each service will be crucial.

The participatory sessions with multiple stakeholders will also be important for this CEC. These will be of two types: (1) to identify needs, motivations and expectations of end-users and other stakeholders; and (2) to envision future scenarios and plan concrete activities that can promote the engagement.

This CEC will focus on:

- Compensating electricity and thermal consumption of the demo by the local Production (PV, H2)
- Producing H2 from the PV panels, store it and use it thanks to the fuel cells
- The hybrid heat pumps installed for heating and cooling of the offices, which run on electricity and/or gas will be exploited to provide the flexibility for improved grid operation
- Install Batteries and additional PVs will be considered for provision of electricity for recharging 2 EV stations

To engage end-users and achieve their high satisfaction with the services implemented, employees will be invited to workshops to codesign posters to be hung in common spaces of the working areas and inform or promote a better understanding and use of energy.

In the future, it is intended to expand the community to include a public car park, the catering service of the business park and proposed services to the municipality.

Phase 5: Legal constitution of the community

Phase 6: Official kick off (by the end of the Neon project).

4. Conclusions

The conclusions of this paper will focus on two aspects. On the one hand, the study of the needs, requirements, and habits of end-users and, on the other hand, the engagement strategies. Likewise, the key result has driven the relationship between the requirements of the users of the CECs and the services, both technological and social/community related.

Thus, in the first place, the survey has proved to be a suitable mechanism for obtaining data and drivers of existing or potential end-users of energy, providing the key information to benefit the individual or at least to refine the bases of the engagement actions and service design.

Likewise, some of the results of the study have set guidelines outside the intuitive framework within the implementation structure of the Energy Communities by confirming that there are divergent aspects with respect to the standard knowledge. The study also leads to the importance of including aspects such as socio-economic level, income range or level of studies. Although these are no vital aspects sine qua non for the development of the sociological study activities prior to the implementation of the engagement strategies, it is considered that they could provide additional and functional information for certain specific applicability frameworks, such as territorial ones.

As far as the engagement strategy itself is concerned, it has been observed that the strategy based on the concluding principles of the sociological study is the fundamental basis of engagement since they establish the guidelines with which the optimal multi-sector adaptations will be defined for each CEC. Likewise, the stratification of phases proposed for the engagement process has proved to be effective as it systematically dynamizes the participation of the target end-users in each of the case studies of the project. Furthermore, these phases not only adapt adequately to the cases of the pilots, but also allow a global scalability of any scenario where the Energy Communities are likely to be applied. This implies that this concept and strategy guideline can be exported to systems of different sizes and socio-cultural characteristics where the divergence will be marked by the feasible results that can be implemented and obtained.

5. Internal review

5.1. Internal Review 1

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes N= no NA = not applicable

Name of reviewer: Javier del Amo

Organisation: Traza Territorio

Date: 10/08/2022

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... contain a list of tables?			X	
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?	X			
... contain an Executive Summary?	X			
... contain a Conclusions section?	X			
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?			X	
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SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT

CONCLUSION

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5.2. Internal Review 2

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Name of reviewer: Philippe Calvez

Organisation: ENGIE

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Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5
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ANNEXES

ANNEX 01: Questionnaire

Cover letter to inform end-users about the project and questionnaire

Neon is a European-funded project that aims to work on the next-generation energy services for Citizen Energy Communities. These communities are legal entities, made of citizens, cooperatives, local authorities, and enterprises, that team up to produce renewable energies.

Within the Neon project, four Citizen Energy Communities will be designed and created: in the municipality of Berchidda (Sardinia island, Italy), where citizens, cork and wine enterprises, and public bodies will conform the community; in Villacañas (Toledo, Spain) to create an Energy Community between enterprises of the industrial park Polígono las Cabezas and residents of the neighbourhood; the residential resort Domaine de la Source (French Alps, France); and the real estate complex for offices, Stains City (France).

To devise how these Energy Communities will be, it is first needed to understand what potential or existing users could benefit from. This questionnaire has the aim of approaching the profile of household or building offices' that will participate in the community, energy-related behaviours, practices, and awareness of potential end-users. Therefore, this questionnaire is directed to citizens, public authorities or enterprises that will potentially participate in the Energy Communities of the Neon project.

Deadline to complete the questionnaire is March 20th.

Questionnaire duration : 20 minutes approx.

Personal data protection. The NEON project partnership ensures the confidentiality and non-disclosure of the data provided in this survey. Data will be used in an aggregated way and only for the purpose of the project.

Want to know more? Please visit NEON WEBSITE or write to (pilot leader email address) for more information about the NEON project.

A. Types of end-users

From the following questions we would like to learn more details relating to your housing/office status.

1 Question

To what Citizen Energy Community will or could you belong to?

- A. Berchidda (Italy)
- B. Villacañas (Spain)
- C. Stains City (France)
- D. Domaine de la Source (France)

2 Question

What is your (potential) relationship with the Citizen Energy Community?

- A. Resident in an apartment/house, that could participate in the Domaine de la Source, Berchidda or Villacañas Energy Communities
- B. User of an electrical car that, in the proximity of the recharging stations of Villacañas
- C. I am part of the municipality of Berchidda, participating in the Italian Energy Community
- D. Worker of an enterprise of Berchidda (Italian community) or Stains City (French community)
- E. Other: _____

3 Question

In which age group do you belong to?

- A. 18-34
- C. 35-64
- F. 65 and up
- H. I prefer not to say.

4 Question

What is your gender?

- A. Male.
- B. Female.
- C. I prefer not to say.
- D. I prefer to be defined as: _____

5 Question

What is your education status?

- A. Early childhood and primary education/ Equivalent
- B. Secondary education/ Equivalent
- C. Tertiary education/ Equivalent or higher

B. Energy-related behaviours

The following questions are concerned with the energy behaviour that mostly represents you. Remember that there are no right or wrong answers, we just want your honest opinion.

6 Question

If your participation in an Energy Community is through your residence, what type of dwelling is it (only residents)

- A. Detached
- B. Semi-detached house
- C. Central House
- D. Apartment building
- E. Other _____

7 Question

If your participation in an Energy Community is through your workplace, what type of building is it

- A. Office buildings
- B. Multi-use
- C. Warehouse
- D. Industrial
- E. Retail
- F. Restaurant
- G. Hotel
- H. Health
- I. Other ____

8 Question

Is the building well insulated?

- A. Yes
- B. No
- C. I don't know

9 Question

Has the building ever been refurbished for energy efficiency?

- A. Envelope
- B. Equipment (HVAC, DHW)
- C. Renewable Energy Source Systems
- D. Never
- E. I don't know

10 Question

How many of the following appliances do you use regularly?

- A. Air conditioning: _____
- B. Water heater: _____
- A. Washing machine: _____
- B. Induction Cooker: _____
- C. Refrigerator: _____
- D. Television: _____
- E. Computer: _____
- F. Water dispenser: _____

11 Question (Only for residents)

How often do you use the washing machine?

- A. Once a day
- B. 2–3 days
- C. One week
- D. Almost never use / I do not have a washing machine

12 Question (Only for residents)

How long do you use the induction cooker in a day?

- A. Less than 30 minutes / I do not have an induction cooker
- B. 30–60 minutes
- C. 1–2 hours
- D. Over 2 hours

13 Question (Only for residents)

How long do you use your television in a day?

- A. Almost never use / I do not have a TV
- B. 1–3 hours
- C. 3–5 hours
- D. Over 5 hours

14 Question

How long do you use your computer in a day?

- A. Almost never use / I do not have a computer
- B. 1–3 h
- C. 3–5 h
- D. Over 5 h

C. Energy practices**15 Question**

What impact does the energy bill have on your household/enterprise budget?

- A. Very high impact
- B. High impact
- C. Medium impact
- D. Low impact
- E. No impact
- F. I do not know

16 Question

What kind of electricity supply tariff does your dwelling or office building have?

- A. Fixed price tariff
- B. Dynamic Tariff (Real time pricing)
- C. Two-block period tariff (peak, off-peak)

- D. More than two-block period hourly tariff
- E. Other:
- F. I do not know.

17 Question

Is energy produced in your dwelling or office building and, if so, what is the nominal power?

- A. Yes, with my own facility: kW
- B. No
- C. I don't know

18 Question

Do you have any of the following smart appliances at home?

- A. Wi-Fi lamps
- B. Smart sockets
- C. air conditioning units
- D. washing machines
- E. water boilers
- F. lighting controllers
- G. television

19 Question

Do you have an Electricity Smart Metre (SM) at home?

(A smart metre is an electronic device that records consumption of electric energy and communicates the information to the electricity supplier for monitoring and billing)

- A. Yes
- B. No
- C. I do not know what kind of metering I have at home

20 Question

What is your main heating system at home?

- A. Heat Pump
- B. Electric radiators with heat storage
- C. Electric radiators without heat storage
- D. Electric portable heaters (with electric resistance)
- E. Gas/ Diesel/ Biomass boiler
- F. Other: _____

21 Question

What kind of cooling system do you have at home?

- A. Air conditioning
- B. Fans
- C. No cooling system
- D. Other: _____

22 Question

What is your main means of transport in your daily life?

- A. Walking
- B. Biking / skateboard / scooter
- C. Car or motorbike
- D. Public transport

23 Question

Do you own an Electric Vehicle EV?

- E. Yes, I have a plug-in hybrid EV (PHEV)
- F. Yes, I have a non-plug-in hybrid EV (HEV)
- G. Yes, I have a pure EV (BEV)
- H. No. I do not have an EV

24 Question

Have you already installed any smart home products at home? (Smart devices are those that can be programmed and can be controlled remotely with an app or web browser).

- A. Smart TV
- B. Smart fridge
- C. Smart washing machine / dishwasher
- D. Smart heating system
- E. Smart cooling system
- F. Other. Please specify:
- G. None

25 Question

Which of the following best describes your energy consumption compared to other tenants?

- A. Consuming more electricity
- B. Consuming slightly more electricity

- C. Neutral
- D. Consuming slightly less electricity
- E. Consuming less electricity

D. Interest in energy

26 Question

How much do you value each of the following aspects, to participate in a Citizen Energy Community?

Rank from 1 to 5, 1 being the lowest and 5 the highest in agreement.

- A. Economic savings on energy expenses because of reduced electricity bills
- B. Support the economy of the local community, such as local workers and commercial activities engaged in energy community activities
- C. Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions that lead to global climate change
- D. Replacing fossil fuels needed for the energy supply of my house with renewable energy sources
- E. Make my own neighbourhood more sustainable and a better place to live in, by improving air quality thanks to the reduction of polluting emissions
- F. Be aware of consumption patterns through the opportunity to trace energy, CO₂, and other forms of environmental savings
- G. Be part of the local community and personal engagement in local community activities, make my own energy plan with neighbours
- H. Gain energy self-sufficiency and become energetically independent
- I. Improve comfort of my own house / apartment / work building
- J. Other (specify) _____

27 Question

Do you think that there is a relationship between energy consumption and environmental protection?

- A. Almost no relationship
- B. There is a certain relationship
- C. There is a tight relationship

28 Question

Would you consider it helpful to know your real-time energy consumption?

- A. Yes, I would like to access it through a Mobile app
- B. Yes, I would like to access it through a Web Browser
- C. Yes, I would like to access it through other means (please specify): _____
- D. No, I do not need or want to access this kind of information, because _____

29 Question

Do you understand your electricity bill statement and charging concepts?

- A. Yes, I fully understand it
- B. Yes, I understand it, with the exception of some concepts
- C. No, I only understand it partially
- D. No, I do not understand it at all
- E. No, but I do not mind

30 Question

Are you familiar with the concept of electricity self-consumption?

- A. Yes, I fully understand it.
- B. Yes, I understand it, with the exception of some concepts
- C. No, I only understand it partially
- D. No, I do not understand it at all
- E. No, but I do not mind

31 Question

Are you willing to participate and benefit from the possibilities of actively being involved in NEON's activities?

- A. Yes, if there is a sufficient retribution
- B. Yes, if it will not affect my comfort levels
- C. No, I am not willing to change my consumption patterns at any time
- D. No, I do not trust external companies accessing my consumption profile and taking control of my home devices remotely
- E. No, I am just not interested at all
- F. I do not know so I have no opinion

32 Question

What of the following statements would make you feel more uneasy to participate in NEON's activities described above, evaluate from 1 to 5 the following statements in your case. 5 most important to 1 least important.

- A. Initial investment.
- B. Possible occasional economic penalties.
- C. Possible misuse of personal information by third parties.
- D. Possible occasional variation of usual comfort preferences.
- E. Financial remuneration lower than initially expected.
- F. Possible new technology failure or malfunctioning.
- G. Lack of transparency of the contract and the remuneration.
- H. Lack of previous user experience in a new business market.

I. Other reasons. Please state: _____

E. Domains for potential energy savings

This section is about your preferences regarding energy savings and your opinion about energy services.

33 Question

Do you think it's possible for you to reduce your monthly energy consumption?

- A. Almost impossible
- B. Small reduction
- C. Significant reduction

34 Question

Would you agree that your electricity retailer (or another company) monitors and automatically operates your electric devices, without negatively affecting your comfort, so you can provide service to the grid?

- B. Yes
- C. No
- D. It depends. Please explain _____

35 Question

Do you want to add something else in relation to your possible participation in the Neon project? Any other remarks?
